

European University Foundation - Campus Europae contribution to the proposed regulation

ERASMUS for all 2014 - 2020

1. Availability of mobility grants per cycle of study

Campus Europae welcomes the increase of the budget dedicated to learning mobility of higher education students and also believes that loan scheme may have positive impacts on learning mobility in Europe. It is however crucial that mobility grants are available for each cycle of study so as to enable students to take advantage of mobility windows both at BA and MA level.

2. Actions for improving the social dimension of ERASMUS

The social selectivity has been a challenge in the ERASMUS mobility for studies, as students with lower income tend to less benefit from it. It is highly recommended to introduce “social criteria” in the attribution of ERASMUS grants, allowing students with low income to benefit from student mobility periods without being afraid of not having enough financial resources.

3. ERASMUS Intensive Language Courses

One of the main achievements of the ERASMUS mobility opportunities is to increase language skills of students when going abroad. These improvements have been widely supported by the ERASMUS Intensive Language Courses. Campus Europae is highly concerned seeing that the funding through the ERASMUS Intensive Language Courses disappeared from the new programme. Indeed, the development of true language policies in Higher Education Institutions is partly based on the funding proposed by the European Commission.

4. Introduce the possibility of combining studying and working while benefiting from a mobility period.

Studying and working at the same time is a reality, about 50% of all European students combine studying and working (Source: Eurostudent 2011) and this for different reasons and for most of them for financial reasons. When going abroad a working student would be forced to leave his job and cause a loss of income, which is not compensated by the ERASMUS grant. This is logically refraining working students from going abroad. Campus Europae recommends thus to allow the combination at the same time of an ERASMUS mobility for placement (part-time work placement) and studies with an increased grant. This would allow a combined social, academic and professional

integration in the host country and additionally reach out students who do not see benefits of only going abroad for study mobility.

5. Mobility with 3rd countries

Campus Europae welcomes the possibility of establishing mobility flows to 3rd countries, which are supported by student mobility grant. It remains however unclear whether those student mobility flows will be treated in the same way as the classical “ERASMUS mobility for studies” flows and how many students will be able to benefit from this opportunity.

6. Double/joint degree master student eligibility for the loan scheme

The renewal of the ERASMUS Mundus experience through the support to joint degree mobility opportunities is a very good step forward. However students undertaking other double/joint degrees programmes are neither eligible for Erasmus nor for Erasmus Mundus grants; this shortfall should be addressed, at least by ensuring their eligibility vis-à-vis the upcoming European loan scheme.